

Event metadata

Event title	Getting started with spatial omics
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	10 September 2025
Time of event	12pm AEST
Topic description	Spatial omics provides unprecedented opportunities for the understanding of cells, tissues and systems by combining omics and imaging technologies. This webinar provides a starting point from which to navigate the evolving field of spatial omics and the numerous methods available. We'll begin with an overview of spatial omics and how it differs from other omics methods. We then explore considerations for analysis of spatial omics data, compare and contrast available tools and delve into some of the theory behind the bioinformatics.
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/spatial-omics-webinar-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Spatial omics
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and bioinformaticians who are curious about spatial omics and how it can be applied in their work.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compare applications of bulk, single cell and spatial omics methods • Describe the features and capabilities of different spatial omics technologies • Outline the process of analysing spatial omics data
Speakers	<p>Dr Michael Geaghan, Australian BioCommons & Sydney Informatics Hub</p> <p>Dr Sarah Williams, QCIF Ltd.</p>
Training materials	<p>Materials shared in this Zenodo record:</p> <p>Slides presented during the webinar: 2025-09-10 Spatial-omics webinar.pdf</p> <p>Materials shared elsewhere:</p> <p>A recording of this webinar is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/fUbXyFFGohg</p>
Related material	None